

Induced Depigmentation in *Bufo melanostictus* and Ascorbic Acid

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Manuscript received 18 September 1979, revised 17 April 1980, accepted 13 April 1981

A low level of ascorbic acid has been shown to be helpful in melanin synthesis in *Bufo melanostictus* while large doses of ascorbic acid are associated with metabolic abnormality leading to poor melanin synthesis.

ASCORBIC acid has been shown to decrease the hyperpigmentation in Addison's disease¹. In black gold fish ascorbic acid inhibits the tyrosinase activity *in vitro*¹. Recently it has been shown that the administration of psoralen, the pigmentogenic furocoumarin causes the lowering of ascorbic acid level in toad liver². The increase of tryptophan pyrrolase under the influence of conventional tyrosinase inhibitors like hydroquinone and catechol has been observed in *Bufo melanostictus*^{3,4}. These effects could be reversed with the administration of psoralen⁴. In consideration of the fact that the action of tryptophan pyrrolase is ascorbate dependent⁵ and there is an inverse relationship between tyrosinase and tryptophan pyrrolase during pigmentation and depigmentation under different experimental conditions, we were interested to undertake the investigations on the effect of different doses of ascorbic acid on these two enzymes in *Bufo melanostictus* and the effect of anti-vitiligo drug psoralen on the effect of ascorbic acid ingested.

Experimental

Materials and methods: Healthy male toads (B. W. 50-70 gm) collected during the summer months were divided into five groups. The groups were named (a), (b), (c), (d) and (e). Now the groups a, b, c, d, e, were treated with ascorbic acid at conc. of 25 mg, 2.5 mg, 0.75 mg, 0.5 mg and 0.1 mg respectively/toad/day for 7 days.

On the 8th day toads from each of the groups were taken and sacrificed to assay the enzymes tyrosinase and tryptophan pyrrolase of the ventral skin and the liver. The toads of each group were then divided into two subgroups. One subgroup was left untreated with psoralen for 7 days, the "Psoralen blank" and the other subgroup was treated with psoralen at a conc. of 1 mg/toad/day for consecutive 7 days.

On the 14th day of the toads of both the subgroups of each group were sacrificed to assay the enzymes tyrosinase and tryptophan pyrrolase of ventral skin and liver.

Tryptophan pyrrolase activity was measured according to the method of Knox⁶ as slightly

modified by Spiegel⁷. The liver and the ventral skin were dissected out. The homogenates of the tissues (12.5%) were prepared with 0.14M KCl containing 0.0025(N)NaOH, pH 7.0-7.5. The homogenate was centrifuged at 20,000×g for 30 mins. The supernatant was used as enzyme source. The enzyme activity was then measured under the following conditions: 0.2M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0 (1 ml), double distilled water (0.7 ml), 0.03M L-tryptophan (0.3 ml), tissue homogenate (2 ml) incubated at 37° for 1 hr. The enzyme activity is expressed in terms of μM of kynurenine/gm of dry tissue weight.

The enzyme tyrosinase was partially purified from ventral skin and liver according to Brown and Ward⁸. Tyrosinase activity of the liver and ventral skin were estimated according to Pomerantz⁹ by measuring the rate of formation of dopachrome from L-DOPA at 37° under the following conditions: L-DOPA (1 μM), sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.4 (35 μM), enzyme (0.2-6.3 units), total 1 ml. The enzyme activity is expressed as unit enzyme/mg of protein.

Results and Discussion

The experiments carried out in *Bufo melanostictus* show that there is a drastic fall of tyrosinase and sharp increase in tryptophan pyrrolase (Tables 1 and 2) activity in the skin and liver in the case of animals receiving 25 mg of ascorbic acid/day/toad for 7 days. This has also been found to be reversed with the administration of psoralen.

At a lower dose level (0.1 and 0.5 mg of ascorbic acid/day/toad for 7 days), little acceleration of tyrosinase and decrease of tryptophan pyrrolase activity (Tables 1 and 2) have been noticed. All the enzyme functions remain normal at a dose level of 0.75 mg/toad/day for 7 days.

Therefore, it is evident that a very low level of ascorbic acid is helpful for acceleration of melanin synthesis in *Bufo melanostictus*. It is conjectural that in human subjects, which cannot synthesize ascorbic acid there may be a minimum requirement of ascorbic acid for maintenance of tyrosinase level or in other words melanin synthesis level. It has been observed that ascorbate can increase

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF ASCORBIC ACID ON VENTRAL SKIN TYROSINASE AND TRYPTOPHAN PYRROLASE ACTIVITY OF *Bufo melanostictus*...±S.E.M., n=10

Dose (mg of ascorbic acid/day/load)	Tissue	Enzyme Activity							
		1		2		3		4	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
25 mg	Ventral skin	96	2.5	0	15	30	10	92	3.0
		±5.12	±0.50		±1.82	±7.07	±0.71	±3.16	±1.12
2.5 mg	Ventral skin	90	2.1	61	5	75	4.1	88	2.5
		±2.24	±0.62	±7.07	±1.21	±2.10	±0.92	±2.60	±0.35
0.75 mg	Ventral skin	95	2.3	96	2.5	98	2.6	97	2.1
		±4.98	±0.73	±7.85	±0.39	±3.83	±1.18	±6.69	±0.92
0.50 mg	Ventral skin	94	2.5	110	2.1	105	2.05	115	2.0
		±5.20	±0.39	±7.07	±0.58	±6.08	±1.11	±7.17	±0.90
0.10 mg	Ventral skin	95	2.3	135	1.8	130	1.25	140	2.0
		±5.34	±1.01	±3.88	±1.08	±4.20	±0.38	±5.30	±0.79

1=Enzyme activity of normal subjects. n=No. of subjects taken per experiment.
 2= " " " treated subjects.
 3= " " " 'Psoralen blank' subjects.
 4= " " " Psoralen treated subjects.
 A=tyrosinase activity, μM of dopachrome $\times 10^{-2}$ /mg of protein.
 B=tryptophan pyrrolase activity, μM of kynurenine/gm of dry tissue wt.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF ASCORBIC ACID ON LIVER TYROSINASE AND TRYPTOPHAN PYRROLASE ACTIVITY OF *Bufo melanostictus*...±S.E.M. n=10

Dose (mg of ascorbic acid/day/load)	Tissue	Enzyme Activity							
		1		2		3		4	
		A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
25 mg	Liver	40	4.6	0	10	10	6.6	36	4.8
		±7.07	±1.08		±1.28	±2.24	±0.70	±4.81	±0.88
2.5 mg	Liver	42	4.6	10	9	13	6.6	36	5.0
		±2.61	±0.71	±2.80	±0.82	±2.40	±2.22	±2.28	±1.08
0.75 mg	Liver	41	4.1	38	4.0	39	5.0	42	4.3
		±2.92	±1.28	±3.03	±0.39	±2.62	±0.85	±2.52	±1.12
0.50 mg	Liver	39	4.5	44	4.1	46	3.9	48	3.8
		±2.32	±1.12	±3.2	±0.97	±2.24	±0.39	±3.16	±1.24
0.10 mg	Liver	40	4.2	50	3.5	48	3.2	52	3.0
		±2.50	±0.92	±3.20	±0.38	±2.87	±0.60	±5.10	±1.01

1=Enzyme activity of normal subjects. n=No. of subjects taken per experiment.
 2= " " " treated subjects.
 3= " " " 'Psoralen blank' subjects.
 4= " " " Psoralen treated subjects.
 A=tyrosinase activity, μM of dopachrome $\times 10^{-2}$ /mg of protein.
 B=tryptophan pyrrolase activity, μM of kynurenine/gm of dry tissue wt.

the tyrosine hydroxylation slightly¹⁰. This being the first step in the conversion of tyrosine to melanin, the result could rationally be explained.

It has been shown by Lewin¹¹ that with the increased dose of ascorbic acid the enzymic cofactors like copper may become less available for the melanin synthesis as it is excreted as copper ascorbate. It is well known that copper activates tyrosinase¹² and deactivates tryptophan pyrrolase¹³. The inactivation of tyrosinase and the activation of tryptophan pyrrolase observed in our experiments could be rationalised on the basis of observation of Lewin. Further, at higher dose due to the presence of a large amount of ascorbic acid, the dopaquinone will be reduced back to DOPA and thus melanin formation will be arrested. In short, it may be concluded that large doses of ascorbic acid are associated with functional metabolic abnormality leading to poor melanin synthesis.

With the application of psoralen, the recovery of the normal state is accelerated. It shows, therefore, that the continuous overdose may adversely affect the normal liver function. Recently Biswas and Roy Chowdhury¹⁴ have claimed that the 25 mg dose of ascorbic acid causes increase of melanin synthesis in *Bufo melanostictus*. Our results do not support their conclusion.

High dose of ascorbic acid has recently been shown to create abnormal functional metabolic disorder in human system¹¹. They have been found to impair essential cation concentration of the body. In consideration of this report, our observation on functional abnormalities of melanin synthesis during high ascorbic acid intake by *Bufo melanostictus* appears to be very rational.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their grateful thanks to

Prof. S. C. Bhattacharyya, Director of Bose Institute and Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Chemistry Department, for their interest in the work.

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